

Innovative processing technologies for bio-based foamed thermoplastics

HORIZON-CL4-2021-TWIN-TRANSITION-01-05:
Manufacturing technologies for bio-based materials

D8.1 PQMP procedures for communication, progress monitoring, quality assurance and risk management

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	description
b-bTPs	bio-based thermoplastics
BP	Business Plan
BM	Business Model
FEA	Finite Element Analysis
FIM	Foam Injection Moulding
CA	Consortium Agreement
DMP	Data Management Plan
GA	Grant Agreement
GenA	General Assembly
EAB	External Advisory Board
EAd	Ethics Advisor
EC	European Commission
ESLM	External Stakeholder Liaison Manager
IM	Innovation Manager
PDEC	Place for Dissemination and Exploitation
PA	Project Advisor
PO	Project Officer
PQMP	Project Quality Management Plan
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

1. Executive Summary

The overall project objectives and activities to deliver results are described in the Grant Agreement (GA). GA and Consortium Agreement (CA) define the management of VITAL project. In this deliverable, the means to manage VITAL project are presented. Furthermore, the ways of communication and project documentation are described. As a final part, the project monitoring is discussed and means to ensure project quality described.

2. Introduction

The overall aim of VITAL is to develop **innovative processing solutions for foamed bio-based Thermoplastics** (b-bTPs), based on three processing value chains that cover the requirements for commercial scale processing in terms of: volume, size, materials, functionality and application. These processes will include:

1. Modification of high-volume production processes that are already highly controlled and automated:
 - a. **Foam Injection Moulding** (FIM) with AI-based process control of instrumented equipment allowing for tight control of critical parameters such as temperature, speed and residence times to ensure part conformity.
 - b. **Bead foaming** of b-bTPs combined with radio-frequency (steam-free) heating.
2. Globally-unique **3D b-bTPs foam printing** for mould-free, additive manufacture for rapid prototyping and bespoke production and massively reduce lead time and costs. The challenges and risks are much higher for 3D printing approach, but the technical and commercial impacts much greater, being a disruptive technology.

Each of these will be realised using optimised formulations of existing and cutting-edge b-bTPs and additives. VITAL will create a globally unique database of foamed b-bTPs properties, that will be critical for further commercial exploitation beyond the project as plug-in data for commercial software such as Moldflow or Moldex3D for injection moulding simulation/optimisation and Abaqus for Finite Element Analysis (FEA) for engineering design of new products/structures. This will enable:

- Mould modelling and design – Pre-process optimisation.
- Process modelling – Pre-process parameter setting to obtain the “best starting point”.
- More accurate modelling and actual in-process control.
- Modelling of final properties (FEA).

In addition, VITAL will achieve commercially viable closed loop, mechanical recycling taking into consideration the specific requirements for b-bTPs.

This deliverable presents the procedures for communication, progress monitoring, quality assurance and risk management of VITAL project. This document supplements GA and CA and complies with the requirements set out in GA and complies with the CA signed by the consortium Parties. The target of this document is also to ensure that project implementation and outputs are of high quality and the code of conduct, standards and good research ethics are followed. This deliverable has a relationship to other activities (or deliverables) in the project that should be considered along with this document for further understanding of its contents (Table 1).

Table 1. Relation to other activities in the project.

Deliverable no.	Contributions
D7.2	This deliverable explains the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication activities
D7.4	This deliverable explains the gender equality plan
D7.5	This deliverable explains the data management plan (DMP)
D8.3	This deliverable explains the ethics management of the project.

3. Management structure and internal communication

The VITAL project is a three-year project, which is divided into eight Work Packages (WPs) as can be seen in Figure 1. Work packages are led by Work Package Leaders (WPL).

Figure 1. Work packages and their interactions in VITAL project (VITAL Methodology showing objectives and outputs).

3.1 Management structure

Grant Agreement (contract between **Consortium Parties** and **EC**) presents the overall project plan including targets and means to achieve the targets. It also presents the management structure of the project. Management structure is important for the successful implementation of the project and for the quality of project results. The Parties of the Consortium have different roles as WP leaders, Task leaders, contributing partners and different managerial positions. Consortium Agreement (contract between Parties) has the purpose to specify with respect to the project the relationship among project Parties, in particular concerning the organisation of the work between the Parties, the management of the project and the rights and obligations of the Parties concerning i.e. liability, access rights and dispute resolution.

Coordinator (VTT) acts as an intermediary between the Parties and EC. In addition, the Coordinator performs its tasks described in GA and CA. The Coordinator's key responsibilities are monitoring compliance by the partners with their obligations, keeping a contact list of project members and other contact persons, collecting, reviewing to verify consistency and submitting reports, other deliverables including financial statements and related certifications and specific requested documents to the Funding Authority, preparing the meetings, proposing decisions and preparing the agendas to the MC and GenA meetings, chairing them and preparing the minutes, monitoring the implementation of decisions taken at meetings, transmitting documents and information connected with the project to

partners, monitoring financial progress, administrating the financial contributions of the Funding Authority.

Consortium agreement defines the specific operational procedures of the main consortium bodies, i.e. **General Assembly (GenA)** and **Management Committee (MC)**. General Assembly (GenA) includes all Parties. It is the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium and has meetings twice a year (F2F and virtually). GenA members were nominated in the project kick-off meeting. Management Committee (MC) includes the Coordinator and WP leaders, and it has quarterly meetings. MC is the supervisory body for the execution of the project, and it monitors the progress of the project in MC meetings. VITAL has eight work packages and they are led by **WP leaders** and WPs can arrange meetings when needed to ensure appropriate progress of the work. WP teams consist of Task leaders and contributors. WP leaders were nominated in the project kick-off meeting. Coordinator chairs all MC and GenA meetings unless otherwise decided.

Project Officer (PO) is the representative of EC and communication with the PO is of key importance for the proper execution of the project. PO needs to be well informed of updates regarding the project, and any possible deviations from the workplan need to be discussed immediately. The Coordinator is the contact between the PO and the Consortium of the project.

Innovation sub-Committee (ISubC) is led by **Innovation manager (IM, Stephen Ryley III)** and **External Stakeholder Liaison Manager (ESLM, Lisa Wikström, VTT)**. Initially, ISubC consists of GenA members. The project also has an **External Advisory Board (EAB)**, which is managed by IM and ESLM. The EAB members will make Non-disclosure commitments, and they can attend GenA meetings upon invitation. The role of EAB is to support the VITAL project in reaching excellence and quality results.

The project also has an **Ethics advisor (EAd)**, which VTT has proposed. This person is Senior Scientist Veikko Ikonen (VTT). He has experience of being an ethics advisor in H2020/HE projects, and he is a member of VTT's Ethical Committee. EAd will monitor the ethics issues involved and how they are handled. EAd will attend project meetings when necessary and will be consulted on all ethical issues. An Ethics plan (D8.3) will be prepared in M4.

3.2 Project communication and documentation

EC's Funding and tenders portal is used for reporting and communication to EC. All official project documents including deliverables are stored in EC's Funding and tenders portal. Coordinator is the liaison between Consortium and EC. VITAL Teams has been created (by VTT) to share and store project documents and for working together. The Coordinator is responsible for the administration of the Teams workspace. All beneficiaries have access rights to the workspace. The Coordinator has ensured that the workspace is safe to use - the Microsoft Teams Workspace is a secure team-wide and organization-wide two-factor authorisation, and single sign-on through the Active Directory-based platform. The data is encrypted in transit and at rest. This Teams workspace includes e.g. project documents, minutes of the meetings, presentations, deliverables and contact list. Also, all contractual project documents (CA, GA) and managerial documents (templates for reporting, meeting documentation and contact list) are stored in there. See Appendix 1 for current the folder structure in Teams. For internal communication and day-to-day communication, also emailing will be used. The Coordinator will prepare minutes of all official meetings, and they will be stored in Teams. The Coordinator will submit all official documents such as deliverables and periodic reports to the EC.

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation are Tasks of WP7. CA defines rules for Dissemination (e.g. publication of results) and Exploitation. Relating to project dissemination and communication, the project website and social media sites (twitter, LinkedIn) have been created:

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/hevitalproject/>

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/VITALHEProject>

Website: <https://vital-project.eu/>

Email: vitalhorizoneurope@gmail.com

Exploitation mechanisms will be defined in WP7 within the iterative **PDEC (Place for Dissemination and Exploitation)**, covering knowledge transfer, commercialisation, and sustainability. PDEC will include: (i) BP and BM (strategic goals); (ii) Market to be addressed; (iii) Routes to market; (iv) Competition and SWOT analysis; (v) Outline of operations plan; (vi) Description of value chain; (vii) Legal, societal and market dependencies; (viii) Financial model and funding requirements. Final PDEC will include future funding requirements for VITAL results, maximizing the chances that this will be secured from public or private sources and that the 'Valley of Death' is overcome. All PDEC versions will cover activities related to dissemination and exploitation that have been undertaken and those still planned.

Dissemination and communication plan, strategy and policy will be agreed (part of PDEC). Targeted activities will be undertaken through existing networks and by exploiting data generated in T7.1.3. Communication activities are undertaken to promote action and dissemination activities of project results. Creation of marketing materials. Website and social media platforms and regularly updated. Video(s) to showcase the project results (complimentary to learning resources). Partner attendance at networking events, workshops, conferences and trade fairs; peer-reviewed publications and magazine/website articles. Final workshop with key stakeholders and value chain partners. Collaborative workshops and meetings with other EC-funded projects, initiatives and EITs; sharing of project data in collaboration with T7.5.

Data management plan (DMP) will be prepared in WP7. The DMP will cover the data management life cycle for all data sets that will be collected, processed, and generated by the project during the project and beyond, and will include the exceptions for open research data. IDENER will define the storage and backup system for data preservation. The DMP will consider the following: (i) Data collection/creation; (ii) Appraisal and selection; (iii) Documentation and metadata; (iv) File Formats; (v) Storage (vi) Ethics: data anonymisation issues; and (vii) Copyright and intellectual property.

Innovation management is a Task of WP7. The innovation manager (IM, Stephen Ryley IIL) coordinates innovation activities through the Innovation sub-Committee (ISubC) to address market and technical issues associated with commercialisation. The ISubC will determine how to protect and exploit IPR using feedback from dissemination and exploitation. The ISubC will provide input for the PDEC development. IM will sign off on confidentiality issues during dissemination and exploitation; undertake 6-monthly meetings (chaired by the Innovation Manager). These meetings will coincide with the 6-monthly MC meetings and will form an integral part of these meetings.

VITAL project has **External Advisory Board (EAB)**, which consists of nominated members. The EAB members will attend yearly meeting (either in person or virtually) to steer the research work towards the ultimate commercial exploitation as well as providing (non-confidential) technical and market information to support the work. The EAB management will fall upon IM with the External Stakeholder Liaison Manager (ESLM) responsible for liaison within the project. Stakeholder mapping and engagement will be undertaken to identify and understand the needs of stakeholders, including industry, the academic community and the general public, in the polymer processing industry. Stakeholder communication and training strategies will follow the EU's inclusive communication guidelines.

4. Progress monitoring, quality control and risk management

Project progress and quality management are continuously monitored for further development and improvement. The WP leaders and Coordinator have important roles to monitor the quality from their perspectives. WP leaders monitor their WPs, and the GenA and the Coordinator monitor the whole project with the assistance of the MC and overlook the technical progress and scientific impact of the project. Managers (including IM, ESLM) and advisors (EAd) monitor their specific area of responsibility, and they are important to ensure proper dialogue and involvement of the identified stakeholder groups, but also monitor the ethical implementation.

Deliverables, milestones and their submission schedule are defined in the Grant Agreement (GA). The immediate responsibility of the appropriate progress of the work and completion of deliverables and milestones is with the WP leaders. Each Deliverable has a Lead beneficiary who is responsible for compiling the report. The WP leader assures that the deliverables are of high quality and are completed in time. In detail, the deliverables need to:

- Correspond to the project and WP objectives
- Be accurate and of high-quality, exhibit good research practices
- Be delivered on time and within the cost constraints planned for the action.

The following deliverable quality process has been agreed: WP leader sends the deliverable to Coordinator three weeks before submission deadline (i.e. uploads the deliverable to the Teams under the Deliverables channel to the WP folder in concern. Coordinator reviews the deliverable and submits the final version to EC. The final pdf and word format versions are stored in Teams under the Deliverables channel by the Coordinator. Document versions should be identified as defined on the Deliverable template. Updating of documents should be done either by using track changes-function or by saving a new version with version number and contributor details.

Based on status information from WP leaders, the Coordinator will assess the achievement of deliverables and report it to the EC and General Assembly. Any deviations and implications due to deviations will also be assessed. If needed, contingency plans will be made if, for example, a delay has occurred that will affect project flow, progress and outputs. If any delays are anticipated, they must be promptly discussed as soon as possible to organise additional resources and if absolutely necessary, to reschedule. For rescheduling, proper justifications are to be provided to the Coordinator, who will discuss and agree with the PO on an alternative submission date.

The key management, implementation and technical (relating to WPs) risks have been identified and will be continuously updated. An iterative process is followed to identify and assess risks, evaluate the risks and make contingency plans, control the risk to avoid the risks as well as mitigate impacts of occurred risks, and finally monitoring and review process is in place to make sure the whole risk-loop functions and possible realisation of risks is caught as early as possible, contingency measures are properly working, and new risks are identified.

Risks have been identified already during the proposal phase, elaborated further during the Grant Agreement Preparation (GAP) phase, as well as in the kick-off of the project. Each WP leader is responsible to monitor their WP for realisation of identified risks or identification of new risks. The foreseen critical risks together with mitigation actions are listed in the Grant Agreement. All consortium partners together with WP leaders are responsible for identifying unforeseen risks. The risk management will be reviewed and managed in each MC (or GenA) meeting.

5. Conclusions

Adherence to the structures and procedures described in this deliverable is important for well-coordinated and appropriate project execution. The project management structure is the management framework of the VITAL project. Without clear management structure and responsibilities, quality project execution is at risk. A clear management structure benefits the project in terms of assessing accountability, outlines the roles, responsibilities and relationships between partners, provides the means for prompt issue management and resolution, and is the foundation for proper and transparent information exchange. The management structure needs to be implemented immediately once the project starts and managed and updated throughout the project life cycle.

The VITAL project governance includes the Management Committee and General Assembly, which have specific complementary roles and divisions among responsibilities and decision-making. General Assembly is the highest decision-making body of the project. Different managerial roles in the project further describe specific responsibilities within the project and ensure proper and successful project execution and results and outreach. The Coordinator has the overall responsibility for executing the General Assembly's decisions and making sure that the work and governance plans are implemented throughout the project and managing and monitor the effectiveness of plans. Important tools and methods for monitoring and assessing the effectiveness are arranging adequate and well-structured meetings, agreed reporting practices, risk assessment and management, proper management of issues at hand and the different communication technologies and means available for the partners (e.g. Microsoft Teams Workspace, e-mails, teleconferences, phone calls, and face-to-face meetings when possible).

Communication with key external stakeholder groups, EAB and the Project Officer, is also important for the proper execution of the project. The Project Officer, representative of the EC, needs to be well informed of updates regarding the project and any possible deviations from the workplan need to be discussed immediately. The outreach to the key external stakeholders EAB and Project Officer of the project is imperative for maximising the potential and outreach of the VITAL project.

All the roles and plans will be constantly monitored and updated by the responsible committees, managers and partners. The VITAL project is well organised with a clear assignment of roles and dedication from all the partners.

Appendices

Appendix 1 – Folder structure in VITAL Teams (existing folders and sub-folders bolded)

VITAL Teams

General

- **Images and photos**
- **Partner logos**
- **Partners and contacts**
- **Project official documents**
- **Project logo**
- **Proposal diagrams**

Deliverables (folder for review and final versions)

- **WP1**
- **WP2**
- **WP3**
- **WP4**
- **WP5**
- **WP6**
- **WP7**
- **WP8**

Management and meetings

- **Advisory board meetings**
- **Financial**
- **General assembly meetings**
- **Kick-off meeting**
- **Management committee meetings**
- **Project progress reports**

Folder for each work package for sharing information, documents and working together

WP1
WP2
WP3
WP4
WP5
WP6
WP7
WP8